

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF CHITOSAN BASED MOISTURIZER

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Abstract

Chitosan is a common polysaccharide familiarly used in biomedical applications in its derivative forms. Chitosan that are obtained from the shrimp shells are taken for the experiment. Chitosan on its own cannot dissolve in any neutral or basic solvents. The major problem chitosan faces is its poor solubility, limiting its applications in various fields. To overcome the solubility issues, a derivative of chitosan known as Carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCh) is synthesized by deacetylation of chitosan and used as a key ingredient for moisturizer. They are used in cosmetic industry due to its capacity to absorb and preserve moisture, antimicrobial characteristics and provide emulsion stabilization. In this study, a number of approaches are used, including antibacterial activity, anti-oxidant activity to detect free radicals and FTIR to identify the functional group in the sample. The formulated cream is applied to alleviate dry skin symptoms and restore a normal function to the stratum corneum. Results indicated that the moisturizer had a good potential as an effective skin moisturizing agent enhancer, antioxidant properties and antimicrobial properties.

Keywords: Chitosan, deacetylation, Carboxymethyl chitosan, cosmetics, emulsion stabilizer.

Introduction

Moisturizers play a crucial role in treating various skin conditions and maintaining skin health. Polysaccharides stand out as one of the most widely used categories of natural polymers in these diverse fields. Carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCH) is a polymer created by adding a carboxymethyl group to chitosan's main structure through a process of carboxymethylation (Jimtaisong *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, numerous oils such as avocado oil possess antimicrobial properties, which are crucial prerequisites for formulating moisturizing products (Woolf *et al.*, 2009). The avocado peel represents a cost-effective and promising resource for extracting phenolic compounds which is used as a natural preservative. Thus, this study sought to investigate the impact of utilizing carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCH) in combination with avocado oil as agents for moisturizing, antioxidant, and antibacterial purposes (Palaniswamy *et al.*, 2021). Various parameters were examined to develop final products, and the efficacy of the cream emulsion system was evaluated.

Materials and Methods

Chitosan from shrimp shells

Shrimp shells were collected and dried in sun for 2 days. After sun drying, the shrimp shells were crispy. Then the shells were grounded into powder. Chitosan preparation is divided into three consecutive steps. Demineralization of Shrimp shells, Chitin processing (Deproteinization) and Chitosan processing (Deacetylation) (Pakizeh *et al.*, 2021).

Chemical modification of Chitosan to Carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCh)

2g of Chitosan was dispersed in 1% acetic acid. 16 ml of 50% NaOH solution was slowly added to the dispersion under stirring and then placed in a freezer for alkalization for 24 h, followed by thawing at 30 °C for 1 h. 5g of chloroacetic acid is dissolved in isopropanol (30 mL) was then slowly added to the dispersion and kept at 30 °C for 3 h. The clear solution in the top was decanted and the white reaction mixture in the bottom was enclosed in a membrane bag for dialysis (for purification) for 3 d. The dialyzed product is called carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCh) (Chaiwong *et al.*, 2022).

Preparation of avocado oil

Avocado fruits are collected and the pulp is scraped and grinded to get a paste. Avocado oil is extracted by microwave heating of pulp and then squeezing and pressing the pulp through a cloth mesh. The pressing step removes as much liquid (press liquor) as possible from the solid. The oil and solid particle fractions are separated by centrifugation (Costagli *et al.* 2015).

Extraction of phenolic compounds from avocado peel

The continuous solid-liquid extractions of avocado peel with a Soxhlet apparatus were performed with 220 mL of absolute ethanol for an avocado sample of 6.11 g, a 1:36 ratio. Evaporation of the ethanol was performed and phenols were obtained (Sara *et al.*, 2022).

Confirmation of phenols

To 2 ml of extract, 2 ml of distilled water followed by 10% FeCl₃ solution was added. Bluish black colour indicated the presence of phenol (Soloway *et al.*, 1952).

Determination of functional group of oil and chitosan using FT-IR

The functional group of the oil and chitosan sample are analyzed by using Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The absorption frequency spectra are recorded and plotted as transmittance versus wave number. FTIR analysis was carried out to know the possible interaction between functional groups of chitosan and avocado oil.

Anti-microbial activity of chitosan and avocado oil

Antibacterial activity of CMCh and avocado oil was carried out using the disc diffusion method against *E.coli* and *S.aureus*. Each test plate comprises of four discs. One positive control, which is a standard commercial antibiotic disc, one negative control, and two treated discs (Muxila *et al.*, 2017) (Afonso *et al.*, 2019).

Anti- oxidant Activity

Briefly, reaction mixtures, containing 1 mL of a chitosan sample (1.0-2.0 mg/mL) in 0.5% acetic acid solution, 1 mL ethanol, and 1 mL of 0.1 mM DPPH ethanol solution, were raised to a final volume of 4 mL by 0.5% acetic acid solution in test tubes. The mixtures were mixed thoroughly and then kept at 25°C for 30 min in the dark. The absorbance of the mixtures was measured at 517 nm against a blank without DPPH using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Si Trung *et al.*, 2015) (Palaniswamy *et al.*, 2011).

Formulation of cream

The moisturizing cream was formulated using two phases: oil phase and aqueous phase along with CMCh. The part A oil phase contains stearic acid, cetyl alcohol and Avocado oil as well as part B liquid phase contains phenols and propylene glycol and sufficient amount of rose water was taken in a beaker separately. Oil phase and aqueous phase were heated at 70⁰ C for few minutes. After cool down, the aqueous phase was mixed in oil phase using mortar and pestel and continuously until smooth and opaque cream was produced (Vignesh *et al.*, 2020). The CMCh, avocado oil and avocado peel extract was added to the cream base at 1% concentration (Mahendran *et al.*, 2014).

Evaluation of the cream

The formulation was evaluated for different pharmaceutical parameters such as pH, homogeneity, appearance, spreadability and skin hydration (Bhide *et al.*, 2005).

Results and Discussions

Chitosan was prepared from shrimp shells by demineralization, deproteinization and deacetylation.

The FTIR spectra of chitosan showed peaks around at 408.91, 432.05, 470.63, 493.78, 563.21, 586.36, 648.08, 686.66, 1527.62 and 2368.59 cm⁻¹. Fourier Transform Infrared spectrum shows characteristic peaks of carbonyl at 1527.62 cm⁻¹ and amide at 2368.59 cm⁻¹ which ensures that this is the FT-IR of chitosan (Zheng *et al.*, 2001).

CMCh was prepared by the reaction of chloroacetic acid with chitosan. Carboxymethylation reactin of chitosan may introduce carboxymethyl groups in the hydroxyl groups bonded to the carbon atoms 3- and 6- of the glucopyranose unit. Avocado oil was extracted by the pressing of heated avocado pulp. FTIR analysis was carried out to know the possible interaction between functional groups of avocado oil. The FTIR spectra of avocado oil showed peaks around at 447.49, 509.21, 555.50, 586.36, 648.08, 686.66, 725.23, 1527.62, 2368.59 and 3749.62. These peaks collectively confirm that the sample is avocado oil .

Antibacterial activity of avocado oil against *S.aureus* in the concentration of 20µl and 40 µl, the zone of inhibition was measured 15mm and 17mm. Antibacterial activity of avocado oil against *E.coli* in the concentration of 20µl and 40µl, the zone of inhibition was measured 5mm and 5mm.

Fig 1: Antibacterial activity of avocado oil against *S.aureus* and *E.coli*

Antibacterial activity of CMCh against *S.aureus* in the concentration of 20µl and 40 µl, the zone of inhibition was measured 20mm and 23mm. Antibacterial activity of CMCh against *E.coli* in the concentration of 20µl and 40µl, the zone of inhibition was measured 18mm and 21 mm.

Fig 2: Antibacterial activity of CMCh against *S.aureus* and *E.coli*

The antioxidant activity of CMCh showed that with increasing concentrations, the scavenging activity has also increased. The increased scavenging percent varies from 55.2 to 70 % (Table 1).

S. No	Concentration of CMCh (μ l)	% of Inhibition of free radical production
1	25	55.2
2	50	63.8
3	75	70
4	100	78.9

Table 1 : Antioxidant activity of CMCh

The moisturizing cream was formulated using two phases: oil phase and aqueous phase along with CMCh. The part A oil phase contains stearic acid, cetyl alcohol and Avocado oil as well as part B liquid phase contains phenols and propylene glycol and sufficient amount of rose water was taken in a beaker separately. The produced cream was smooth and opaque (Table 2). The CMCh, avocado oil and avocado peel extract was added to the cream base at 1% concentration. Evaluation of formulated cream was done by determining its pH, appearance, irritability, colour, consistency, stability and skin hydration. The pH of the cream was found to be in range of 7.1 which is good for skin pH. The prepared cream showed good characteristics in terms of appearance on the visual inspection of the formulation. Without the use of any coloring agents, the cream came out to be a pale white color. The consistency of the formulated cream was smooth. Cream stored at different temperature were stable in its colour, consistency, odour. After the application of moisturizer, the skin appeared smoother, softer and more supple. The skin retained moisture for a period of 5 hours after applying the moisturizer. With the above data it can be concluded that the cream produced from chitosan derivative has potential characteristics of a good moisturizer.

Polysaccharides have been reported in recent years to have various cosmetic activities such as moisturizing, whitening, anti-aging and repairing skin. This study uses chitosan derivative for the formulation of moisturizing cream. Chitin, the precursor was processed by deproteinization followed by chitosan processing. FTIR results showed the presence of carboxyl and amino groups which possess the film forming ability and hydrating characteristics. Chitosan, apart from its typical biopolymer characteristics such as biocompatibility, biodegradability, and non-toxicity, possesses several distinctive qualities. However, a limitation to its utility, particularly in cosmetics, is its insolubility in water, necessitating improvements in solubility through chemical modifications such as carboxymethylation.

Chitosan was chemically modified to carboxymethyl chitosan (CMCh) to increase its solubility in water. Antibacterial activity of CMCh against *S.aureus* and *E.coli* showed significant zone of inhibition. Antioxidant activity was estimated to have found the free radicals present in the sample.

Avocado oil was prepared from the pulp of avocado fruit. Phenols extracted from the avocado peel was used as a natural preservative. Cream was formulated using oil phase and aqueous phase by oil in water emulsions. Oil phase includes stearic acid, cetyl alcohol and avocado oil whereas aqueous phase includes phenols, propylene glycol and rose water.

Ingredients	Composition of formulation	Function on formulation
Active ingredient		
CMCh	5 ml	Film forming
Oil phase		
Stearic acid	4 g	Emulsifier
Cetyl alcohol	5 g	Humectant
Avocado oil	2 ml	Emollient
Aqueous phase		
Phenols	1 ml	Preservative
Propylene glycol	8 ml	dissolving agent
Rose water	q.s	fragrance

Table 2 : Composition of moisturizing cream

Evaluation of the cream was done by measuring several parameters such as pH, colour, odour, homogeneity etc. The chitosan derivative used to formulate the moisturizer is safer showed ideal results. The result showed that the formulation of moisturizer contain all good characters of an ideal moisturizer and it is found to be harmless, more effective and cost effective.

Conclusions

CMCh was proven to be a successful polymer in maintaining skin hydration for a longer duration compared to water, propylene glycol, and natural chitosan. Furthermore, incorporating avocado oil extract with CMCh into emulsion creams demonstrated promising potential as an efficient enhancer for skin moisturization, along with exhibiting antibacterial and antioxidant properties.

T. No	Concentration of CMCh (μ l)	% of Inhibition of free radical production
1	25	55.2
2	50	63.8
3	75	70
4	100	78.9

Table 1 : Antioxidant activity of CMCh

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